

Influence of Managerial Competencies of Administrators on Resource Management in Secondary Schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State

Musa Inusa YIDAWI¹, Lateefah Adeola ALABI² and Abubakar Abubakar BABAJI³

¹Department of Physical Science Education, Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria

²Department of Business Administration, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria

³Department of Science Education, Air Force Comprehensive School, Yola, Nigeria

Abstract:- This study examines the influence of managerial competencies of administrators on resource management in secondary schools in fagge and nasarawa local government areas of kano state. The study involved 79 principals from public secondary schools within Fagge and Nassarawa Local Government Area. Descriptive survey design was employed, data collection utilized a 26-item questionnaire titled "Managerial Competencies of Administrators on Resource Management in Secondary Schools (MCARMSS)." Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in determining the reliability of the instrument, resulting in a coefficient of 0.69. The findings revealed a lack of managerial competencies among secondary school administrators in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Area of Kano State in areas such as hiring qualified teachers, orienting new staff and students, ensuring well-furnished classrooms, delegating financial matters effectively, and implementing cost-saving strategies for efficient human and material resource management. However, the study also identified managerial competencies in administrators for prioritizing financial allocation based on school needs, maintaining accurate financial records, generating detailed financial reports, and involving department heads in budget preparation for effective financial resource management. In light of these findings, the study recommends that school administrators actively acquire and consistently apply managerial competencies. Additionally, it suggests adopting a democratic approach to school management and pursuing further training in financial management skills as crucial steps toward enhancing overall competence in resource management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Issues related to resource management are tremendous; they range from inadequate staff, material scarcity, and financial insufficiency to political and economic constraints (Mohammed & Lawal, 2020). Management involves organizing human, material, and financial resources to attain specific goals and objectives. Akinfolarin (2017) asserts that Management is the arrangement of available human and material resources for achieving desired goals and objectives. Achieving goals hinges on effective utilization of organizational resources. The primary administrator of a secondary school is the principal; he plays an essential role in the school's daily functions. He is responsible for making informed decisions which will impact the school's success and educational outcomes (Supriadi, Usman, Jabar, & Widyastuti 2021). These decisions encompass curriculum development, resource allocation, extracurricular activities, and more. By exercising sound judgment and considering the best interests of students and the school community, the administrator contributes to the overall growth and advancement of the school. According to Akinfolarin (2017), administrators, such as principals, head masters, proprietors, etc., are leaders responsible for planning, coordinating, and supervising school affairs to ensure smooth operation. The principal is the chief administrator of secondary school who is expected to effectively use various resources through the adoption of management principles and practices for the realization of school goals (Akinfolarin, 2017). Administrators at every level of schools must ensure the effective management of human, material and financial resources to enable the attainment of national policies and goals of the education system.

Olaleye (2013) emphasizes that the principal, serving as the chief executive in secondary schools, should have the competencies to make sound decisions that align with the need of the school and benefit the staff as a whole. Competency is a series of knowledge, abilities, skills, experiences and

behaviors which leads to effective performance in activities (“Competency” 2023). Competency refers to the capability and skills essentials to fulfill assigned tasks or roles. (Akinfolarin, 2017). To attain favorable results, school administrators need to acquire competencies in management of crucial assets within their respective schools. Successful management requires the administrator to juggle various tasks commonly encountered in the school setting. Executing these tasks effectively involves acquiring specific competencies. Therefore, the manner in which an administrator handles these responsibilities to reach the goals of the school reflects their competency level and serves as a distinct representation of their leadership style (Nyakan, 2018).

One of the school administrator's core functions is that of resource management. These resources include human resources (staff and students), material resources (classrooms, equipment, supplies), and financial resources (budget management, fundraising). Effective management of these resources is crucial in maintaining the school's functionality and achieving its goals. Akinfolarin (2017) asserts that, human resource management in the school system encompasses two key areas: staff human resource management and students' human resource management. Efficiently managing both staff and students not only enhances productivity but also ensures the achievement of goals. Material resources are those objects that must be present and effectively managed to enhance the achievement of educational goals and objectives. It includes school facilities such as buildings, laboratories, libraries, e-learning tools, instructional materials, furniture, classrooms, offices, school records, sports facilities, etc., all of which contribute to effective teaching and learning processes. (Oyeleye & Ayodele, 2022).

Financial management involves the planning, sourcing, and prudent utilization of school funds. Principals, being the chief accounting officers in schools are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring the judicious use of school funds by applying various financial management competencies (Egboka & Igbokwe, 2021). Alia & Iwuoha (2014) stress that effective financial management by school administrators involves prioritizing funding based on needs, aligning budgets with goals, delegating financial tasks to capable staff, closely monitoring delegated responsibilities, adhering to budget constraints, strategically planning and acquiring funds for school development, maintaining precise financial records, and presenting an unbiased financial overview of the school.

Changing trends in the education sector demands school administrators to adjust to the evolving environment for sustainable long-term viability. Many school administrators are still in the process to familiarize themselves with the digitalized and contemporary methods of school management. In light of this context, the study tends to examine the influence of administrators managerial competencies on the management of secondary school resources in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria.

➤ *Statement of the problem*

Secondary school is essential as it lays the groundwork for further academic endeavors, career training, and entering the profession. In order to achieve the best possible educational results, administrators must manage people, material, and financial resources well. Research indicates that the competencies of administrators play a significant role in shaping the quality of education. Nevertheless, secondary schools face a lot of challenges, including incomplete syllabus coverage, teacher tardiness, conflicts, student truancy, and insufficient facilities and funding (Akinfolarin, 2017). These issues may stem from administrators deficient managerial competencies, hindering the necessary organizational changes required for improvement. With this in mind, this study examined the influence of managerial competencies of administrators on resource management in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria.

➤ *Purpose of the Study*

The aim of this study is to examine the influence of managerial competencies of administrators on resource management in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine:

- The influence of managerial competencies of administrators on human resource management in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria.
- The influence of managerial competencies of administrators on material resource management in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria.
- The influence of managerial competencies of administrators on financial resource management in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria.

➤ *Research Questions*

- What managerial competencies do administrators need to effectively manage human resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria?
- What managerial competencies do administrators need to effectively manage material resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria?
- What managerial competencies do administrators need to effectively manage financial resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria?

II. REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES RELATED TO THE STUDY

Many studies have investigated related topic, often within specific geographical or subject constraints. In a study conducted by Bitterová, Hašková, and Pisonová (2014) titled *School leaders competencies in the management area in Slovakia*. The researchers investigate the competencies of school leaders in the management area in Slovakia. Employing a descriptive survey research design, the study population comprises all school leaders in Slovakia, with a sample of 93 school leaders selected for data collection. The research utilizes a 16-item questionnaire for data collection, and descriptive statistics were used in data analysis. The findings indicated that practicing school leaders consider competencies related to creating motivational strategies based on shared values, developing an effective learning environment, defining responsibilities and delegating tasks, and leading and controlling colleagues as the most significant in the management area.

A study conducted by Akinfolarin (2017) in Anambra State titled *"Analysis of Principal's Managerial Competencies for Effective Management of School Resources in Anambra State,"* was to examine principals' managerial competencies for secondary school resource management that works. The research design of the study was a descriptive survey, and it was driven by three research questions. All 257 secondary school principals in Anambra State made up the study population, thus no sampling technique was used to draw from the complete group. The *"Principals' Managerial Competencies for Effective Management of School Resources Questionnaire (PMCEMSRQ)"*, a tool created by the researcher and face verified by three professionals, was used to collect data. Its Cronbach alpha value of 0.85 indicated good reliability. The data were analyzed by mean and standard deviation. The study revealed that secondary school principals in Anambra State lacked managerial competencies in procuring physical and instructional materials, providing e-library facilities, and equipping classrooms and offices with needed furniture for effective material resource management. However, they exhibited competencies in prioritizing financial allocation, maintaining accurate financial records, ensuring accountability in expenditures, conducting periodic budget audits, and adopting cost-saving strategies for effective financial resource management.

A study carried out by Abdul, Kazi & Aziah (2018) titled: *Headmaster's Managerial Roles Under School-Based Management and School Improvement: A Study in Urban Secondary Schools of Bangladesh*. The research aimed to elucidate the school-based management system in urban areas of Bangladesh, while also testing hypotheses regarding the relationship between the role of school principals and school quality improvement. Additionally, their study seeks to determine the relationship between teacher professional development and school quality enhancement. Four research

questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study population consisted of 10634 teachers from all the 315 secondary schools in Dhaka, Bangladesh. A sample involving 127 school principals and 694 teachers were used for the study through purposeful and stratified random sampling technique. The research data was collected through questionnaires from urban secondary schools in Bangladesh. The data analysis employed linear and multiple regression methods. The research findings indicate that several factors related to the leadership role of school principals have a significant impact on improving school quality and enhancing teacher professionalism. Maximum improvement in school quality can be achieved when schools prioritize collaboration among teachers, provide training in service delivery, and maintain continuous monitoring of classrooms, while reducing emphasis on individualistic actions. The best prediction for improving school quality is obtained through a comprehensive design and the role of the school principal as a facilitator through school-based management. Teacher collaboration and classroom monitoring have a positive and significant influence on improving school quality.

Ali, Arshad, & Rasool (2019) conducted a study titled *"The effective management of secondary school head teachers in Punjab province, Pakistan, through a comparative study."* Using a survey research design, the study looks at how well secondary school head teachers are managed in Pakistan's Punjab region. The province's senior secondary school teachers (SSTs), both male and female, and district-level education officers are the study's target audience. 464 senior SSTs were chosen using multistage random sampling, and structured interviews and questionnaires are used to gather data. With a reliability value of 0.83, the instrument's consistency is deemed satisfactory. In data analysis, the mean, standard deviation, and percentage are employed. The results showed that head teachers who were directly chosen by the Punjab Public Service Commission were more effective at managing the school than head teachers who were promoted, particularly when it came to increasing enrollment and achieving better outcomes.

Darwansah, Fitria, & Setiawan (2021) conducted a study titled *"The Effect of Principal Managerial Competence and School Facilities on Teacher Performance" in Cluster I Dewi Sartika Baturaja Timur, Indonesia*. The purpose of the study was to ascertain how school infrastructure and principal managerial competency affect teacher performance. Three research objectives form the basis of the study's ex post facto research design. All elementary schools in Cluster I Dewi Sartika Baturaja Timur make up the population, while 97 instructors from SD Negeri in Sekayu District, Musi Banyuasin Regency, make up the sample. Multiple regression and quantitative descriptive analysis approaches are used in data analysis. The results show that the availability of school amenities and principal managerial competency have a substantial impact on the performance of SD teachers in

Cluster 1 Dewi Sartika Baturaja Timur. Furthermore, in Cluster 1 Dewi Sartika Baturaja Timur, Indonesia, the combined impact of principal management competency and school amenities on teacher performance was also significant.

A study carried out by Nchida & Omenyi, (2021) in North-West Region, Cameroun titled, Principals’ resource management practices as correlates of school performance in public secondary schools in north-west region, Cameroun. The resource management strategies used by principals and academic achievement in public secondary schools in Cameroon’s northwest were shown to be related by the study. The study was led by four hypotheses and four research questions. The research design used in the study was correlational survey. All 132 principals of government technical schools in Cameroon’s NW region made up the study population. The distribution of the population in the region’s seven divisions is as follows: Boyo has fifteen principals; Bui has twenty-one; Donga Mantung has eighteen principals; Menchum has eleven principals; Mezam has thirty-five principals; Momo has fifteen principals; and lastly, Ngoketunjia has seventeen principals. Since every member of the population was included in the study, no sampling strategy was employed. The instrument used for data collection was “Principals’ Resource Management Practices Questionnaire (PRMPQ) validated by three experts. PRMPQ reliability was determined by Cronbach alpha to be 0.73. Study-related data were answered using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). The study’s conclusions showed that, in the North West Region of Cameroon, there is a strong positive link between school performance and principals’ management of human resource practices, school finance practices, physical resource practices, and instructional materials resource practices.

In a study conducted by Gamala & Marpa (2022) titled "School environment and school heads’ managerial skills: Looking into their relationships to school’s performance," in Philippines. The research examines the influence of school environment and school heads' managerial skills on school performance. The study used a descriptive correlation method and was directed by three objectives. There are 115 school administrators, 1044 teachers, 115 students, and 115 parents in the population. Data are gathered using two sets of

questionnaires totaling 106 items, and the sample size was calculated using Slovin's technique. After three experts evaluated and standardized the instruments, high Cronbach alpha values of 0.93 and 0.95 were obtained. The questionnaire items were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation, and the relationship between the school environment, the managerial abilities of the school heads, and the performance of the schools was investigated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). The outcome shows that school performance and the managerial skills of school heads are both highly regarded, and the school climate was deemed to be rather positive.

III. METHOD

The study employed a descriptive survey research design, commonly known as non-experimental research. The population consisted of all principals of public secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa local government areas of Kano State, totaling 79 principals. Due to the manageable size of the population, no sampling technique was applied. The research utilized a 26-item questionnaire titled "Managerial Competencies of Administrators on Resource Management in Secondary Schools (MCARMSS)" structured into three sections. The first section focused on 9 items related to administrators' competencies in managing human resources, the second section included 8 items on competencies in managing material resources, and the third section comprised 9 items on competencies in managing financial resources. Responses were recorded on a 4-point Likert scale (Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Strongly Disagreed, Disagreed). The questionnaire underwent face and content validation, and reliability assessment using test-retest yielded a Person moment correlation co-efficient of 0.65.

IV. RESULTS

The research questions were answered and presented as shown in the table below:

Research Question 1: What managerial competencies do administrators need to effectively manage human resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria?

Table 1; Mean and standard deviation scores of managerial competencies administrators need to effectively manage human resources in secondary schools.

S/N	Items	mean	SD	Decision
1.	Ensuring good working condition of services for the staff	1.82	0.71	Disagreed
2.	Involving staff for decision making	3.20	1.01	Strongly agreed
3.	Assigning specific roles and setting clear goals	2.14	0.94	Agreed
4.	Ensuring staff attend seminars and workshops outside schools	2.92	0.73	Agreed
5.	Giving bonuses in form of cash as form of motivation to staff	2.63	0.79	Agreed
6.	Ensure better and qualified staffs are employed	1.90	0.81	Disagreed
7.	Ensuring discipline among teachers and students.	2.06	0.91	Agreed
8.	Offering incentives to students as a means to enhance academic performance.	2.82	0.81	Agreed

9.	Introducing new staff and students to school activities and objectives.	1.34	0.70	Disagreed
----	---	------	------	-----------

Mean of mean and standard deviation 2.31 0.82 Agreed

In table 1, item 2 indicates the respondent strongly agreed with the statement while item 3,4,5,7 and 8 indicates that the respondent agreed with the statement. Item 1 and 2 were disagreed by the respondents. The grand mean score is 2.31 which indicate that the administrators’ managerial competencies to effectively manage human resources in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria were average.

Research Question 2: What managerial competencies do administrators need to effectively manage material resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria?

Table 2; Mean and standard deviation scores of managerial competencies administrators need to effectively manage material resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1.	Ensure school library is always Equipped with study material	2.15	0.96	Agreed
2.	Ensure school facilities are updated and upgraded to confirm with modern standard.	2.22	1.16	Agreed
3.	Ensure school facilities are renovated from time to time	2.72	0.85	Agreed
4.	Should ensure adequate security Is provided to prevent vandal Of schools properties	2.06	0.94	Agreed
5.	Ensure laboratories are provided	2.11	0.88	Agreed
6.	Ensure that classroom are well furnished	1.89	0.77	Disagreed
7.	Ensure teaching aids and other instructional materials are arrange in order of utilization	2.01	0.76	Agreed
8.	Assign competent officers to Responsible for the security of Educational materials and Instructional materials in schools	2.24	0.79	Agreed

Mean of means and standard deviation 2.17 0.88 Disagreed

In table 2, the respondents indicate agreement with the statement of item 1,2,3,4,5,7 and 8 while the respondents disagree with statement of item 6. Based on the grand mean, the administrators’ managerial competencies to effectively manage material resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria were above average.

Research question 3; What managerial competencies do administrators need to effectively manage financial resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria?

Table 3; Mean and standard deviation scores of managerial competencies administrators need to effectively manage financial resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	mean	SD	Decision
1	Involving heads of department in budget preparation	2.08	0.76	Agreed
2	Ensuring that financial allocation aligns with specific needs.	3.09	0.85	Strongly agreed
3	Performing detailed financial reporting	2.10	0.84	Agreed
4	Delegating financial matters to capable staff	2.00	0.79	Disagreed
5	Ensure operating within the confines of the school budget.	2.81	0.89	Agreed
6	Sourcing of funds for development projects	1.92	0.75	Disagreed
7	Ensure accountability in all school	1.96	0.72	Disagreed
8	Maintaining accurate financial records for the school.	2.79	0.84	Agreed
9	Adopting cost saving strategies	1.99	0.69	Disagreed

Mean of means and standard deviation 2.30 0.79 Agreed

In table 3, the respondents strongly agreed with the statement of item 2 while item 1,3,5, and 8 were agreed by the respondents. Item 4, 6, 7 and 9 were disagreed by the respondents. The grand mean indicates that administrators' managerial competencies to effectively manage financial resources in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria was average.

V. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the findings presented in Table 1, administrators of secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria exhibit managerial competencies in effective human resources management. This was evident in their practices of involving staff in decision-making, assigning specific roles with clear goals, ensuring staff attendance at seminars and workshops beyond the school premises, providing cash bonuses as motivation to staff, maintaining discipline among teachers and students, and offering incentives to enhance students' academic performance. Based on the mean values of 2.31 obtained, the administrators of secondary schools are competent in managing human resources. This is consistent with the findings of Akinfolarin (2017), who noted that administrators of secondary schools in Enugu State showed proficiency in human resource management. Comparable results were also reported by Nnebedum & Egboka (2017), who found that human resources management strategies were used by secondary school principals in Enugu State. These strategies included staff participation in decision-making, supervision of teachers' delivery of instruction in the classroom, recognition of staff for exceptional performance, and monitoring of staff truancy levels to encourage school attendance. These results corroborate those of Olaleye (2013), who highlighted that competent school administrators assign tasks to capable personnel and include their staff in decision-making. He went on to say that effective managers inspire collaboration and loyalty in their workforce.

Based on the results presented in Table 2, administrators of secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria, expressed agreement regarding the importance of ensuring the school library is well-equipped with study materials, updating and upgrading school facilities to conform to modern standards, regularly renovating school facilities, and providing adequate security to prevent vandalism of school properties. However, respondents disagreed with the proposition of ensuring that classrooms are well-furnished. Administrators in secondary schools in Kano State's Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas lack the managerial skills necessary for efficient management of material resources, as indicated by their mean value score of 2.17. This finding is consistent with research conducted in Anambra State by Akinfolarin (2017), which found that secondary school principals lacked the administrative skills necessary for efficient material resource management. Similar findings were made by Nnebedum and

Egboka (2017) in Enugu State, who found that principals in that state did not sufficiently implement a number of material resources management measures to improve secondary schools.

Based on the outcomes detailed in Table 3, respondents in Fagge and Nasarawa Local Government Areas of Kano State, Nigeria, concurred with specific items, revealing that administrators prioritize involving Heads of departments in budget preparation, ensuring financial allocation meets needs, conducting thorough financial reporting, adhering to the constraints of the school budget, and maintaining accurate financial records for the school. The mean value score of 2.30 implies that administrators demonstrate managerial competencies for effective financial resource management in secondary schools in Fagge and Nasarawa local government of Kano state. This finding aligns with Alia & Iwuoha's (2014) assertion that any school administrator must excel at managing finances effectively. Additionally, Lipham (2016) supports these conclusions, emphasizing that financial management skills are crucial for school principals to excel in planning, sourcing, and utilizing school funds. Nevertheless, this finding contradicts the report of Mirti & Wangui (2014), which suggested that financial management remained a challenge for secondary schools.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the insights garnered from this study, it can be inferred that administrators in secondary schools within Fagge and Nasarawa local government areas of Kano state, Nigeria demonstrate managerial competencies in the realms of effective human and financial resource management. The study affirms that these administrators exhibit competencies in proficiently overseeing human and financial aspects within the school setting. However, a noteworthy conclusion drawn from the research is that these administrators lack the requisite managerial competencies for the effective management of material resources in Fagge and Nasarawa local government areas of Kano State, Nigeria. This deficiency suggests a potential area for improvement in the administrators' competencies, particularly in addressing the challenges associated with material resource management within the educational context.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Drawing upon the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- Implementing training programs for administrators to enhance their managerial competencies, leading to a more balanced and efficient approach in overseeing human, material, and financial resources.
- Ensuring constant supervision and finding other means of checking conformity to the managerial competencies acquired by the administrators can also enhance the effective management of the school resources.

- The administrators should adopt democratic approach to school management due to its participating and interactive nature.
- The administrator should also be trained on various financial management competencies that can help on sustaining and managing the school resources more effectively.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Akinfolarin A.V (2017) *Analysis of Principals Managerial Competencies for Effective Management of School Resources in Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria*. International Journal of Social Sciences, Humanities and Education 1(4)236-245
- [2]. Ali M. S, Arshad M, and Rasool S. (2019) *Effective management of secondary school headteachers in Punjab province: A comparative study*. Global Regional Review (GRR) Vol. IV, No. III (Summer 2019) | Page: 136 – 144 | DOI: 10.31703/grr.2019 (IV-III).15 e-ISSN: 2663-7030
- [3]. Alia, C.O. & Iwuoha, N.S. (2014). *New challenges facing Imo state secondary school principals in a decentralized system: The way forward*. Journal of Educational Research, 2(3), 179 – 187.
- [4]. Bitterová M, Hašková A, and Pisonová M, (2014) *School Leader's Competencies in Management Area in Slovakia*. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 149 (2014) 114 – 118. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/266562870> on 20 July, 2023
- [5]. Competency (Human Resources). (2023, June 17). In Wikipedia. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Competence_\(human_resources\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Competence_(human_resources))
- [6]. Darwansah E., Fitriah H. and Setiawan A. A. (2021) The Effect of Principal Managerial
- [7]. Competence and School Facilities on Teacher Performance. Journal of Social Work and Science Education Volume 2 (2) 2021 E-ISSN: 2723-6919 P-ISSN: 2746-0827
- [8]. Egboka P.N and Igbokwe I. C (2021) *Principals' Application of Administrative Competencies for Effective Management of Secondary Schools in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State*. International Journal of Education and Evaluation E-ISSN 2489-0073 P-ISSN 2695-1940 Vol 7. No. 3 2021.
- [8]. Gamala, J. J., & Marpa, E. P. (2022). *School environment and school heads' managerial skills: Looking into their relationships to school's performance*. International Journal on Social and Education Sciences (IJonSES), 4(2), 218- 235. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijonSES.285>
- [9]. Lipham, J. (2016). *The principalship: Foundations and functions* (3rd ed.). Harper and Row
- [10]. Miriti J.M, Wangui N.M (2014) *Financial Management; Training Needs of Secondary School Principals In Machakos County, Kenya*. Research on Humanities and Social Sciences 4(13)136-141
- [11]. Mohammed A and Lawal N (2020) *Resource Management Skills Needed By Principals Of Secondary Schools In Yobe State, Nigeria*. International Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies 8(3):45-53, July-Sept, 2020
- [12]. Nchida D.S. and Omenyi A.S, (2021) *Principals' resource management practices as correlates of school performance in public secondary schools in north-west region, Cameroun*. Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. Retrieved from https://phd-dissertations.unizik.edu.ng/repos/81200845200_103937081856.pdf on 15 July, 2023
- [13]. Nnebedum C, & Eboka P.C (2017). *Analyses of Resources Management Strategies Adopted by Principals for Secondary Schools Improvement in Enugu State Nigeria*. International Journal of Advanced Research And Innovative Ideas in Education 3(3) 4124-4129
- [14]. Nyankan B.A (2018) *Influence of Principals Management Competencies on Quality of Education in Public Secondary Schools In Homa Bay County, Kenya*. Phd Thesis Kisii University, Kenya.
- [15]. Olaleye, F.O. (2013). *Management competence: Need for effective professionalization of Nigerian secondary school principals*. Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review, 2(10), 49-54
- [16]. Oyeleye B.O and Ayodele J.B (2022) *Availability of educational resources and principals' managerial effectiveness in secondary schools for educational sustainable development in southwest, Nigeria*. Journal of Economic, Social and Educational Issues, Vol.2. No 2, June 2022 ISSN: 2158-8125
- [17]. Supradi D. Usman H. Jabar A. & Widyastuti I. (2021) *Good School Governance: An Approach to Principal's Decision-Making Quality in Indonesian Vocational School*. Research gate.